

**TECHNIQUES FOR NON-INVASIVE IDENTIFICATION OF TEXTILES AND
NONCONVENTIONAL COMPOSITE MATERIALS**

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ABSTRACT

The analytical techniques allow proposing interventions in the studied material, conveying advantageous characteristics for technical textiles, and different types of composites used in engineering as well as understanding the degradation process of the material. The present study aimed to evaluate the main physicochemical analytical techniques (FTIR and Raman) employed in the characterization of textile and nonconventional composite materials. The methodology consisted of a systematic literature review carried out in Web of Science and Scopus database. As result analytical techniques, particularly non-destructive ones can reveal different phases of composites, impurities, and modifications following treatments such as alkaline treatment. They can also provide useful information about material composition, even materials with highly similar chemical compositions, as plant fibers may be distinguished using analytical methods and multivariate statistical analyses.

Keywords: nonconventional materials; textiles; non-invasive techniques; microscopy; FTIR; Raman.

INTRODUCTION

The identification of cellulose fibers plays an important role in recycling, industry, and museums, especially for the development of new materials and certification of their physical and chemical properties (Chen; Lin; Tan, 2019. Meleiro, 2016. Houck, 2009. Sinclair 2015; Garcíá-Ruiz, 2016. PEETS et al., 2017).

The function and value of the clothing depend on the quality of the employed fabric. In this way, knowing the material type employed in fabric production is of paramount validity. In addition, it is necessary to confirm the properties expected for the material, such as regain, flammability, strength, and crystallinity. For a composite, adhesion and compatibility between phases, and performance before and after interventions such as alkaline treatments on fibers. Some techniques also allow revealing, besides the textile quality, clues to elucidate the material production processes (Kozłowski, 2020; Peets et al., 2017).

The textile characterization by non-destructive analytical techniques is elemental for several areas such as forensic science and museology, in which the possibility of destroying a part of the sample becomes undesirable and impracticable, mainly because it does not allow the result reproducibility (Chen; Lin; Tan, 2019; Peets et al., 2017).

Textile recycling is also a topic relevant for characterization context. Global production reached around 120 million tons in 2019 (GmbH, 2020;(Palacios-Mateo et al., 2021)), being the textile and clothing industry the 4th largest one in the world. As a result of the decrease in the average time of clothing wear, there is an increase in the production and consumption of textiles and, on the other hand, the recycling industry of these materials does not grow at the same rate (Roser, 2019; Nikolina, 2019). One of the important factors for the recycling industry is the possibility of identifying and separating textiles on large scale, which is not feasible by techniques widely spread and known as optical analysis, chromatography, and thermal analysis, but is possible by other techniques such as Infrared (IR) and Raman vibrational spectroscopy (Margariti, 2019a; Hospodarova, 2018).

Museums are spaces where the preservation and conservation of these different textiles are waiting for researchers to elucidate their mysteries with different questions (Paula, 2006). The characterization of these textiles from the cultural-historical heritage makes it possible to identify these materials, collaborating not only with the conservation and protection of the material but also corroborating with historians and anthropologists (Paula, 2006).

Microscopic, thermogravimetric, and chromatography techniques often require fiber samples, which are not always available for historical heritage or archaeological textiles. On the other hand, infrared (IR) and Raman vibrational techniques provide valuable information about the composition and structure, which allows the identification of unknown material characteristics (Balbas et al., 2022).

Among different kinds of textile materials, the identification of cellulose fibers is a necessary process to guarantee the quality and the desired characteristics, but it can be a difficult process due to the similarities in the fiber compositions (Kaito, 2021). About these similarities that affect mainly the infrared spectrum (IR), some articles have reported that it is possible to differentiate cellulosic fibers using different statistical software presenting different, but high assertiveness rates (Kaito, 2021; Mäkelä et al., 2021; Kengo, 2021).

Faced with the needs of different areas, but which present similar problems and questions about characterization, the present study aimed to verify how analytical techniques of FTIR and Raman are being applied to the characterization and identification of different cellulosic materials. In addition, to present their applications for new materials, such as composites and application in different areas, identifying the main potentialities and limitations of analytical characterization techniques applied to textiles in different areas, including new materials, industry, recycling, heritage, and forensic science.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology consisted of a systematic literature review carried out on Web of Science, Google Scholar, and Scopus database in which the following keywords were searched on these platforms: composites, textile fibers, textiles characterization, non-invasive techniques, microscopy, FTIR, and Raman.

The literature analysis aimed at applications of characterization technologies applied in textiles for different areas and about the use of the techniques with the focus on the identification of the modified characteristics after treatments, application in new materials, textile conservation, and forensic applications. Therefore, the article was subdivided into the following topics subheading: (i) Vegetable Fiber and Applications: Analysis of FTIR and Raman; (ii) Vibrational analytical tests on forensic materials; (iii) Conclusion.

RESULTS

Vegetable Fiber and Applications: Analysis of FTIR and Raman

Fibers from plant origin are made up of cellulose, lignin, pectin, and hemicellulose. Cellulose is semi-crystalline, being responsible for the hydrophilic characteristic. Hemicellulose is an amorphous and

partially water-soluble polysaccharide and hemicellulose joins cellulose forming microfibrils. Lignin, like hemicellulose, is hydrophobic and is responsible for rigidity (Ali et al., 2018).

The tensile strength and intrinsic properties of cellulosic fibers are provided by the cellular structure, the responsible part being the intermediate layer of the second wall. However, these characteristics depend on the degree of polymerization, cellulose amount, and smaller angle of the microfibrillar (Abdul Khalil et al., 2017).

Many natural fibers have been studied for use in applications such as composite reinforcement. The fibers commonly used for composites are sisal, coconut fiber, hemp, jute, and flax. Table 1 presents these main cellulosic fibers produced are presented by type, origin, species, producing countries, and production (Fang et al., 2020; Kohan et al., 2022).

Table 1: Annual natural fiber production of main cellulosic fibers applied to composites.

	Fiber type	Origin	Species	Largest producer countries	World production (10³ tons)
	Coir	Fruit	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	India, Vietnam, Sri Lanka	100
	Kenaf	Stem	<i>Hibiscus cannabinus</i>	India, Bangladesh, United States	970
	Flax	Stem	<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	Canada, France, Belgium	830
	Bamboo	Stem	(>1250 species)	China, India, Indonesia	30,000
	Abaca	Leaf	<i>Musa textilis</i>	Philippines, Ecuador, Costa Rica	70
	Jute	Stem	<i>Corchorus capsularis</i>	India, Bangladesh	2500
	Sisal	Leaf	<i>Agave sisalana</i>	Tanzania, Brazil, Kenya	378
	Ramie	Stem	<i>Boehmeria nivea</i>	China, Brazil, Philippines	100
	Hemp	Stem	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	China, France, Philippines	215
	Pineapple	Leaf	<i>Ananas comosus</i>	Philippines, Thailand, Indonesia	74

Sources: (Lotfi et al., 2021; Sanjay et al., 2016; Kohan et al., 2022)

The non-destructive analytical and physical performance characterization techniques are important tools since they allow the identification at a structural level of the modification after treatments (Pires et al., 2012; Kathiresan & Meenakshisundaram, 2022).

Regarding the possibility of orthopedic, dentist, and constructive surgical applications, (Parida et al., 2015), treated the *Luffa cylindrica* fiber with modified alkaline treatment employing calcium carbonate and calcium phosphate aiming for application as a reinforcement phase in nanocomposites. For the characterization of the fiber of *Luffa cylindrica* fiber, these authors analyzed FTIR and Raman spectra in the regions of 500 - 4000 cm⁻¹ and 300 - 3000 cm⁻¹ respectively, showing the lattice structure of cellulose, both crystalline and amorphous. To find the degree of crystallinity after the modified alkaline treatment, they analyzed the ratio of the intensity of the peaks of 1454 cm⁻¹ and 893cm⁻¹, obtaining a 74.12% crystallinity degree for cellulose. The Raman technique confirmed the presence of calcite and

hydroxyapatite, calcium carbonate, and calcium phosphate polymorphs, respectively, in the treated modified cellulosic fibers that can be used as bioactive materials.

Some recent studies have shown that the analytical techniques of FTIR and Raman are associated with PCA (Principal Component Analysis) and LDA (Linear Discriminant Analysis) statistical analysis. Generically, LDA explicitly attempts to model the difference between the classes of data whereas PCA, in contrast, does not take into account any difference in class, and factor analysis builds the feature combinations based on differences rather than similarities. In some cases, the statistical treatment with Fisher has shown to be efficient for the identification and classification of vegetal textile and regenerated cellulose fibers (Makela, 2021; Kengo, 2021).

The PCA and FDA statistical techniques extract the features of the spectra clearly in a two-dimensional plane, the spectra without the statistical treatments are difficult to visually distinguish. PCA is often used as a method of extracting spectral features, allowing to draw a fine comparison of correlation or non-correlation between the spectra of the observed samples (Makela, 2021; Kengo, 2021).

Spectroscopic analysis techniques such as those mentioned above, such as FTIR and Raman, accompanied by multivariate analysis techniques such as principal component analysis (PCA), and Fisher's discriminant analysis (FDA), can analyze and discriminate materials with very similar compositions as in the case of vegetable or synthetic textile fibers allow the identification and classification of a large number of materials, offering identification and grouping in a short time, allowing garments with different fiber mixtures to be classified on an industrial scale (Makela, 2021; Kengo, 2021).

Other fibers such as wool and silk are also being identified by vibrational spectroscopic techniques associated with the multivariate statistical treatment, the PCA treatment was able to identify and discriminate cotton, wool, and silk fibers from yarns commonly used in the production of tapestries and rugs. from antiquity available in the sample database of the Tapestry and Rugs Conservation Laboratory of the Opificio Delle Pietre Dur (Florence, Italy) (Quintero Balbas et al., 2022a).

Regarding the potential for fiber characterization and identification related to chemical functional groups and structure, FTIR and RAMAN vibrational techniques are also contributing to the identification and conservation of mineralized textiles found in excavations (Margariti, 2019). Because these techniques are non-destructive, they could be used on heritage materials confirming that the textiles were still undergoing active decay, but that there was good preservation of the organic matter within the fibers. FTIR together with Raman proved capable of detecting bands attributed to compounds characteristic of the organic matter present and preserved in the fibers, as well as, bands attributed to the degradation of organic matter and the effects of mineralization (Chen; Jakes; Foreman, 2016; Margariti, 2019).

Composites

For a long time, mainly clay bricks were reinforced with straw, shells, or even steel alloys. Since the middle of the 20th century, this class of material began to be differentiated. It presented the combination of different materials during the manufacturing process, which allowed the creation of a wide range of new materials combining the properties of the different materials involved in the process (M. Li et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2016). Composites are multiphase materials, most of them are made from two phases: one called the matrix and, the other one called the dispersed phase or reinforcement. Both phases can be from different materials. The matrix can be polymeric, metallic, ceramic, or carbonaceous, depending only on the intended application. The reinforcement phase can be fibrous or polymeric (Yan et al., 2016).

Environmental concerns about the need of creating new friendly environmental and energy-efficient materials, cellulosic fibers have been widely used as alternatives to steel or synthetic fibers as reinforcements in cementitious composites. These cellulosic fibers include flax, sisal, jute, hemp,

coconut, hibiscus, cannabinus, eucalyptus pulp, mallow, ramie, pineapple leaf, kenaf bast, sansevieria leaf, avocado leaf, vakka (*Roystonea regia*), bamboo, banana tree, palm fiber, sugar cane, etc. (Aziz et al., 1984; Cook et al., 1978; Ghavami et al., 1999; Keer, 1984; Silva et al., 2010; Tan et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2012; Yan & Chouw, 2012b)

Taking into account technological advancement and demands for materials with higher performance and multiple functions, fiber-reinforced composites have taken up significant space in different areas such as the civil industry employing different fibers. Regarding natural fibers for potential use and application in composites, banana, jute, and sisal fibers have been analyzed for composite reinforcement (Y. Li et al., 2000; Pothan, 2003; Ranan et al., 2003).

Characteristics and modifications in fibers will vary depending on the final purposes and potential applications. To achieve a final application, the fibers should present some requirements and engineering attributes, thus guaranteeing the best performance. For example, in the aerospace industry, properties such as high strength and tenacity are necessary. Then the most suitable fibers for these requirements are carbon or glass fibers. If the requirement is fire retardancy, in this case, aramid fiber is the most advantageous (Pothan, 2003).

Composites reinforced with natural fibers have become an interesting alternative to replace metals or composites reinforced with synthetic fibers. This is mainly due to the demand for lighter materials that cause less environmental impact. Compared to man-made fiber, vegetable fibers present high advantages, such as density, greater biodegradability, excellent damping properties, and offering less abrasive damage to equipment, which makes them good alternatives for matrix reinforcement (Ogin, 2016).

The employed methods for fiber processing are usually related to the textile industry process. However, for composite applications, new materials have been developed, such as fibers and bundles glued together by a chopped blanket or continuous thread (Nijssen, 2015). Reinforced cement matrix fabrics (FRCM) with synthetic reinforcements have been used in a wide range of precast products on the market, with emphasis on two product lines: (i) architectural (no load), as external cladding systems, facades, walls, and panels; (ii) structural elements (load carriers), such as bridges, and reinforcing cement pipes (Papanicolaou, 2016). Other applications are still possible, because of the use for masonry (Carvalho Bello et al., 2019).

As plant fibers are polar and hygroscopic, they are incompatible with most polymeric matrices, causing difficulty in the fiber/matrix interface adherence. To minimize this problem of fiber adhesion, alkaline or other treatments are commonly employed. Furthermore, the effectiveness of fiber adhesion needs to be certified. The FTIR analytical technique allows for identifying changes in fiber composition before and after alkaline treatment. For example, Figure 1 shows the spectrum for natural sisal fiber (SINAT), sisal fiber treated with a 2% solution of sodium hydroxide (SINAT 2%), and with 10% solution (SINAT 10%). In the spectrum, it is possible to find bands in the range of 3460 – 3434 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the O-H bond. In the treated fibers (SINAT 2% and SINAT 10%), it is possible to notice that the area under the spectrum increased considerably, confirming that there was an increase in O-H after the alkaline treatment (Sueila, 2009). Figure 1 still shows a shift in the peak of the bands in the range 1745-1734 cm^{-1} , which is attributed to the vibration of the carbonyl group of the hemicellulose.

Figure 1: Spectrum for sisal fiber: natural (SINAT) and treated with an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide 2% (SINAT 2%) and 10% (SINAT 10%) (Sueila, 2009).

Several fields of composites and nano-composites applications are possible. Normally, these selections require the crossing of information about techniques, which can provide all the information about the potential of the material, especially involving new materials, such as those that depend on comfort and safety (Pieroni et al., 2017; United Nations Environment Programme, 2020).

According to product launching, which is useful to daily routine and, still with the sustainable concern, materials must not have toxic substances for human conditions in their composition, nor that generate pollution. These lines of products are being created for traditional raw materials substitution (United Nations Environment Programme, 2020).

The effectiveness of some oxide metallic and clay have been studied to incorporate into the polymeric matrix, to act as fire-retardant. In the meantime, there is the problem of post-consumer, due to these polymeric materials be long to degrade in the environment. Facing this problem, plant fibers incorporation can be an alternative to this technology. With the joint incorporation of minerals in fibers of cotton fabric, combined with the presence of phosphorus and nitrogen compounds an alternative proposed to obtain a more sustainable flame retardant finish compared to the existing ones, the flame retardant properties were mainly due to the presence of the nano-hybrid composite (Oliveira, 2020).

The FTIR spectra for the cotton fabric coated with the kaolinite-TiO₂ nano-hybrid composite indicated the presence of silanol-type chemical groups (Si-OH); siloxane (Si-O-Si); Si-O-C; P-O-C; C-N and N-H and many layers of TiO₂ bound to cellulose, which proves the chemical changes caused on the surface of the fibers of the kaolinite- TiO₂ treated fabric. In this treatment, the cotton fibers support less thermal degradation concerning the untreated fabric. Thus, for this proposal of fiber impregnated with nanocomposite, the FTIR technique proved to be important to show the modifications carried out in the kaolinite and the effectiveness of the experimental methods used (Felinto, 2018).

The textile sector has a large volume of solid and liquid waste from industrial processes. Another problem is in the disposal and recycling of postconsumer. According to the tendency to develop new materials with a green footprint and rethink postconsumer or reuse discarded material, the civil construction sector has researched solutions for fabrics and fibers, such as in the production of cement composites reinforced with textile waste (Felinto, 2018).

Vibrational analytical techniques combined with other techniques such as thermogravimetric, microscopy, and x-ray diffraction contribute to the composite properties' identification, with the emphasis on investigating adhesion between phases matrix and dispersed fibers. The investigation of the reinforcement phase between fibers and cementitious matrix, viscose textile residues, and carbon resulted that fiber obtained good results, which achieved 0.5% of compressive strength and acquired more strength over 28 days, the fibers still allowed the non-disaggregation of the cement matrix after the breaking load, noted the ability of the fibers to avoid cracks propagation (Felinto, 2018).

The FTIR technique allowed the identification of different phases of the composite both the viscose fiber and carbon fiber residue, being possible the discrimination in the FTIR spectrum (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Figure FTIR-ATR spectrum of residue and carbon fiber sample (Felinto, 2018).

Focusing on the growing trend of recycling and the possibility of using this material for new composite development, which is in line with sustainable development, the civil industry has tested the capacity and functionalization of these new materials in different composite uses, contributing to environmental protection and saving non-renewable raw material resources (Hospodarova et al., 2018; Kathiresan & Meenakshisundaram, 2022; Oliveira, 2020).

The characterization for analysis of the physical properties and chemical composition of the fibers is a necessary step since the composites require a strong fiber with maximum adhesion and between the phases to improve these properties if necessary (Hospodarova et al., 2018; Kathiresan & Meenakshisundaram, 2022; Oliveira, 2020).

For the analysis of materials with very similar chemical compositions, FTIR and Raman techniques are shown as an option mainly because they provide an answer to the composition of the material and are not destructive techniques. The test of six samples of cellulose with different types of processing coming from wood pulp and recycled (wood processing—the sulfate bleached beech tree cellulose; GW500, W640, and G250WT) and (recycling waste paper as newspapers, magazines, and cartons; G500T, G700T, and G3/00T) shown in Figure 3 (Hospodarova et al., 2018).

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of wood pulp cellulose fibers compared to microcrystalline cellulose (MC) (Hospodarova et al., 2018).

The statistical analyzes of the spectra in Figure 3 showed differences in the contents of organic components such as cellulose, hemicelluloses, and lignin, as well as in the presence of inorganic impurities (calcite and kaolinite) from the paper manufacture process (Hospodarova et al., 2018).

Vibrational analytical tests on forensic materials

Textile fibers are a key form of evidence trace, and the ability to reliably associate or discriminate against them is crucial for forensic scientists around the world (Goodpaster, 2009). The infrared diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) technique together with Raman spectroscopy has allowed the characterization and identification of dyed textile fibers, enabling the identification of chemical classes of the material, bringing additional information about the material contributing to forensic work. (Kirkbride K, 1999; Kokot, 1997; White, 1999).

Vibration spectroscopic techniques are highly suitable for the identification and comparison of textile fibers and clothing fabrics. On the other hand, new chemical imaging modes based on these spectroscopic techniques are becoming useful in various fields. This is particularly important for, for example, visualizing and chemically tracking different samples, including forensic evidence (Quintero Balbas et al., 2022b).

Visual microscopic examination of textile fibers is recommended by forensic experts as it allows rapid differentiation of fibers based on their morphological characteristics. However, discrimination of fibers based on their perceptible color and other non-specific visual properties is not always possible. In these cases, spectroscopic vibrational techniques are used (Causin et al., 2005; Sano & Suzuki, 2009). Different studies have shown the possibility of applying Raman and infrared techniques in different textile materials associated with crime scenes, with these techniques bringing information that contributes to solving the crime (Cantrell et al., 2001; Causin et al., 2005; Goodpaster, 2009; Wiggins; Drummond; Champod, 2004; Yan; Chouw, 2012).

The fact that there is expressive research in forensic chemistry. However, many of them are in restricted or internal publications in security agencies, making it difficult to have a dimension of the possibilities of analyzes and situations that benefited from the characterization of textiles by non-destructive analytical techniques such as the Raman and FTIR (Branco et al., 2013)

The Raman micro-spectroscopy technique associated with the multivariate statistical techniques proved capable of differentiating and discriminating fibers and fabrics, even when they presented very similar compositions such as 100% cotton in samples such as gauze and t-shirts, which may imply additional chemical differences beyond those provided. by the manufacturer on the composition of the materials, which opens the possibility in forensic analysis to differentiate a sample coming from the criminal's clothing or from another sample, opening up margins for use in quality control tests (Zapata et al., 2022).

The FTIR technique has proved to be of great value because is a non-destructive technique that allows reproducibility. Beginning research reports from the 50's highlight the advantages of using the FTIR. At that time, Raman spectroscopy was still not widespread for economic reasons and was associated only with basic research, such as the determination of molecular symmetry. It was only disseminated and commercialized from the 1990s onwards (Brettell et al., 2005).

Taking into account the recognition of the analytical potential of IR spectroscopy, it was possible to cheap and develop interferometric equipment (FTIR), as well as the development of accessories that allowed the study of smaller amounts of samples and improvements in the signal and noise ratio (Alexiou et al., 2012).

Fibers occupy the place of traces most frequently found in the collection of samples for this fact, they stand out in the themes of investigation in forensic science. Generally, the FTIR technique in the ATR

module is the most chosen for analysis, although the detection of dyes is obscured by the fiber signal. In this case, the Raman technique presents more advantages (Grieve, 1988).

CONCLUSION

Analytical techniques, especially non-destructive ones, constitute a powerful arsenal for the characterization of textile fibers, composites, and new materials. The characterization by these techniques allows, in addition to providing information on the composition and structure of the material, to give the possibility of perceiving subsequent modifications to alkaline and modified alkaline treatments, for example.

Within the possible information provided by the analytical techniques, it is the possibility of identifying materials with different phases such as composites and fabrics with different proportions of textile fibers. Associated with statistical techniques, it was possible to identify and group different fibers, but almost identical compositions.

New materials need to be analyzed in different tests to verify if their physical and chemical properties meet the expectations, large and small changes throughout the preparation of the material are eventually necessary, and the non-destructive analytical techniques have proved to be efficient in being sensitive to these changes, proving to seem efficient for industry and different areas of science. The best choice of analytical technique is associated with the question that one intends to ask and the degree of the expected answer. Different areas benefit from the possibility of characterizing and identifying textile fibers, which allows different uses for the fibers and the development of new materials, thus being able to manipulate their characteristics. The comparison of the information collected in the literature allowed the comparison of the potential and limitations of these techniques.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the funding by CAPES (“Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior” - Brazilian Federal Agency for Support and Evaluation of Graduate Education).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- Abdul Khalil, H. P. S., Tye, Y. Y., Saurabh, C. K., Leh, C. P., Lai, T. K., Chong, E. W. N., Nurul Fazita, M. R., Hafidz, J. M., Banerjee, A., & Syakir, M. I. (2017). Biodegradable polymer films from seaweed polysaccharides: A review on cellulose as a reinforcement material. *EXPRESS Polymer Letters*, 11(4), 244–265. <https://doi.org/10.3144/EXPRESSPOLYMLETT.2017.26>
- Amaziah Walter Otunyo, & Nnodi Dan Nyecheio. (2017). Mechanical Properties and Fracture Behaviour of Coconut Fibre Reinforced Concrete. *American Journal of Civil Engineering and Architecture*, 208–216. <https://doi.org/10.12691/ajcea-5-5-5>
- Andreas, W. Engelhardt. (2020). The Fiber Year 2020, GmbH, (2020). Deceleration along the textile chain. *International Fiber Journal*. <https://fiberjournal.com/the-fiber-year-2020-deceleration-along-the-textile-chain/>

- Balbas, D. Q., Lanterna, G., ... C. C.-T. E. P., & 2022, undefined. (n.d.). Non-invasive identification of textile fibres using near-infrared fibre optics reflectance spectroscopy and multivariate classification techniques. *Springer*. Retrieved April 12, 2022, from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02267-1>
- Branco, R. do C. P. de O., Alexiou, A. D. P., Faria, D. L. de A., Toma, H. E., Sarkis, J. E. de S., Branco, M. de O., Pedrozo, M. de F., Moreira, P. E., & Salvador, V. L. R. (2013). Química Forense Sob Olhares Eletrônicos (2a). Millennium.
- Brettell, T. A., Butler, J. M., & Saferstein, R. (2005). Forensic science. *Analytical Chemistry*, 77(12), 3839–3860. https://doi.org/10.1021/AC050682E/ASSET/AC050682E.FP.PNG_V03
- Cantrell, S., Roux, C., Maynard, P., & Robertson, J. (2001). A textile fibre survey as an aid to the interpretation of fibre evidence in the Sydney region. *Forensic Science International*, 123(1), 48–53. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738\(01\)00520-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0379-0738(01)00520-5)
- Causin, V., Marega, C., Schiavone, S., & Marigo, A. (2005). A quantitative differentiation method for acrylic fibers by infrared spectroscopy. *Forensic Science International*, 151(2–3), 125–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FORSCIINT.2005.02.004>
- Chen, H. L., Jakes, K. A., & Foreman, D. W. (2016). SEM, EDS, and FTIR Examination of Archaeological Mineralized Plant Fibers: <Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1177/004051759606600406>, 66(4), 219–224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/004051759606600406>
- Chen, H., Lin, Z., & Tan, C. (2019a). Classification of different animal fibers by near infrared spectroscopy and chemometric models. *Microchemical Journal*, 144, 489–494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MICROC.2018.10.011>
- Chen, H., Lin, Z., & Tan, C. (2019b). Classification of different animal fibers by near infrared spectroscopy and chemometric models. *Microchemical Journal*, 144, 489–494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MICROC.2018.10.011>
- Cook, D. J., Pama, R. P., & Weerasingle, H. L. S. D. (1978). Coir fibre reinforced cement as a low cost roofing material. *Building and Environment*, 13(3), 193–198. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1323\(78\)90043-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1323(78)90043-4)
- Fang, Z., Li, B., Liu, Y., Zhu, J., Li, G., Hou, G., Zhou, J., & Qiu, X. (2020). Critical Role of Degree of Polymerization of Cellulose in Super-Strong Nanocellulose Films. *Matter*, 2(4), 1000–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MATT.2020.01.016/ATTACHMENT/D72BF4C4-48AD-4732-BF63-DCFC8EA32F0A/MMC1.PDF>
- Ghavami, K., Toledo Filho, R. D., & Barbosa, N. P. (1999). Behaviour of composite soil reinforced with natural fibres. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 21(1), 39–48. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-9465\(98\)00033-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-9465(98)00033-X)
- Goodpaster, J. v. (200 C.E.). *Forensic Analysis of Dyed Textile Fibers Selective Fluorescence Quenching View project Canine Detection of Explosives View project*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-009-2885-7>
- Hospodarova, V., Singovszka, E., & Stevulova, N. (2018). Characterization of Cellulosic Fibers by FTIR Spectroscopy for Their Further Implementation to Building Materials. *American Journal of Analytical Chemistry*, 09(06), 303–310. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajac.2018.96023>

- Kathiresan, S., & Meenakshisundaram, O. (2022). Effect of alkali treated and untreated cellulose fibers and human hair on FTIR and tensile properties for composite material applications. *SN Applied Sciences*, 4(3), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S42452-022-04946-9>/FIGURES/10
- Keer, J. G. (1984). FIBRE REINFORCED CONCRETE. *New Reinf Concr*, 52–105.
- Kohan, L., Coelho, L. S., Baruque-Ramos, J., & Savastano Junior, H. (2022). Cellulosic Fabric-Reinforced Cementitious Matrix (FRCM): Ligaments, Treatments, and Employment. *Materials Circular Economy 2022 4:1*, 4(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S42824-022-00052-8>
- K. Saito, T. Yamagata, M. Kanno, N. Yoshimura and M. Takayanagi, Spectrochim. Discrimination of Cellulose Fabrics Using Infrared Spectroscopy and Newly Developed Discriminant Analysis Acta, Part A, 2021, 257, 119772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2021.119772>
- Kozłowski, R., & Mackiewicz, M. (2020). Handbook of Natural Fibres - 2nd Edition. In *Volume 1: Types, Properties and Factors Affecting Breeding and Cultivation*. <https://www.elsevier.com/books/handbook-of-natural-fibres/kozłowski/978-0-12-818398-4>
- Li, M., Pu, Y., Thomas, V. M., Yoo, C. G., Ozcan, S., Deng, Y., Nelson, K., & Ragauskas, A. J. (2020). Recent advancements of plant-based natural fiber-reinforced composites and their applications. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPOSITESB.2020.108254>
- Li, Y., Mai, Y. W., & Ye, L. (2000). Sisal fibre and its composites: a review of recent developments. *Composites Science and Technology*, 60(11), 2037–2055. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538\(00\)00101-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(00)00101-9)
- Lotfi, A., Li, H., Dao, D. V., & Prusty, G. (2021). Natural fiber-reinforced composites: A review on material, manufacturing, and machinability. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 34(2), 238–284. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0892705719844546>
- Margariti, C. (2019a). The application of FTIR microspectroscopy in a non-invasive and non-destructive way to the study and conservation of mineralised excavated textiles. *Heritage Science* 2019 7:1, 7(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40494-019-0304-8>
- Margariti, C. (2019b). The application of FTIR microspectroscopy in a non-invasive and non-destructive way to the study and conservation of mineralised excavated textiles. *Heritage Science*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-019-0304-8>
- Mäkelä, M., Rissanen, M., & Sixta, H. (2021). Identification of cellulose textile fibers. *Analyst*, 146(24), 7503–7509. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1AN01794B>
- Meleiro, P. P., & Garcíá-Ruiz, C. (2016). Spectroscopic techniques for the forensic analysis of textile fibers. *Applied Spectroscopy Reviews*, 51(4), 258–281. <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2015.1132720>
- Nijssen, R. P. L. (2015). Composite Materials: An introduction. In Holland University of durable sisal fiber-cement composites. *Constr Build Mater* 2010;24(5):
- Ogin, S. L., & Potluri, P. (2016). Textile-reinforced composite materials. In R. A. Horrocks & S. A. Anand (Eds.), *Handbook of Technical Textiles* (2nd ed., pp. 1–26). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-78242-465-9.00001-X>
- Oliveira, C. (2020). *Acabamento retardante de chamas em tecido de algodão a partir da incorporação de um compósito nano-híbrido caulinita-TiO2 via processo solvotermal* [Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina]. <https://repositorio.ufsc.br/handle/123456789/230873>

- Palacios-Mateo, C., van der Meer, Y., & Seide, G. (2021). Analysis of the polyester clothing value chain to identify key intervention points for sustainability. *Environmental Sciences Europe 2021* 33:1, 33(1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S12302-020-00447-X>
- Paula, T. C. Fabrics and their conservation in Brazil: museums and collections. Publisher of the publication Teresa Cristina Toledo de Paula. Sao Paulo: Museu Paulista da USP, 2006a
- Parida, C., Dash, S. K., & Pradhan, C. (2015). FTIR and Raman Studies of Cellulose Fibers of *Luffa cylindrica*; *Open Journal of Composite Materials*, 05(01), 5–10. <https://doi.org/10.4236/OJCM.2015.51002>
- Peets, P., Leito, I., Pelt, J., & Vahur, S. (2017a). Identification and classification of textile fibres using ATR-FT-IR spectroscopy with chemometric methods. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 173, 175–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SAA.2016.09.007>
- Peets, P., Leito, I., Pelt, J., & Vahur, S. (2017b). Identification and classification of textile fibres using ATR-FT-IR spectroscopy with chemometric methods. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 173, 175–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SAA.2016.09.007>
- Pires, E. N., Merlini, C., Al-Qureshi, H. A., Salmória, G. v., & Barra, G. M. O. (2012). Efeito do Tratamento Alcalino de Fibras de Juta no Comportamento Mecânico de Compósitos de Matriz Epóxi. *Polimeros*, 22(4), 339–344. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-14282012005000053>
- Pieron, M. C., Leonel, J., & Fillmann, G. (2017). RETARDANTES DE CHAMA BROMADOS: UMA REVISÃO. *Quim. Nova*, 40(3), 317–326. <https://doi.org/10.21577/0100-4042.20160176>
- Pothan LA, Oommen Z, Thomas S (2003) Dynamic mechanical analysis of banana fiber reinforced polyester composites. *Compos Sci Technol* 63:283–293. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538\(02\)00254-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(02)00254-3)
- Quintero Balbas, D., Lanterna, G., Cirrincione, C., Fontana, R., & Striova, J. (2022a). Non-invasive identification of textile fibres using near-infrared fibre optics reflectance spectroscopy and multivariate classification techniques. *European Physical Journal Plus*, 137(1). <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-02267-1>
- Quintero Balbas, D., Lanterna, G., Cirrincione, C., Fontana, R., & Striova, J. (2022b). Non-invasive identification of textile fibres using near-infrared fibre optics reflectance spectroscopy and multivariate classification techniques. *European Physical Journal Plus*, 137(1). <https://doi.org/10.1140/EPJP/S13360-021-02267-1>
- Rana AK, Mandal A, Bandyopadhyay S (2003) Short jute fiber reinforced polypropylene composites: effect of compatibilizer, impact modifier and fiber loading. *Compos Sci Technol* 63:801–806. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538\(02\)00267-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(02)00267-1)
- Reis J (2006). Fracture and flexural characterization of natural fibre-reinforced roofing material. *Build Environ* 1978;13(3):193e8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2005.02.008>
- Sanjay, M. R., Arpitha, G. R., Naik, L. L., Gopalakrishna, K., & Yogesha, B. (2016). Applications of Natural Fibers and Its Composites: An Overview. *Natural Resources*, 07(03), 108–114. <https://doi.org/10.4236/nr.2016.73011>
- Sano, T., & Suzuki, S. (2009). Basic forensic identification of artificial leather for hit-and-run cases. *Forensic Science International*, 192(1–3), e27–e32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FORSCIINT.2009.08.018>

- Silva, F. de A., Filho, R. D. T., Filho, J. de A. M., & Fairbairn, E. de M. R. (2010). Physical and mechanical properties of durable sisal fiber–cement composites. *Construction and Building Materials*, 24(5), 777–785. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONBUILDMAT.2009.10.030>
- S. Nikolina (2019) European Parliamentary Research Service Environmental impact of the textile and clothing industry: What consumers need to know. European parliament. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2019/633143/EPRS_BRI\(2019\)633143_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2019/633143/EPRS_BRI(2019)633143_EN.pdf)
- Sueila, S. et al (2009) Effect of fiber modification on the mechanical properties of pp/sisal composites processed by extrusion. Proceedings of the 10th Brazilian Polymer Congress. <https://www.ipen.br/biblioteca/cd/cbpol/2009/PDF/1267.pdf>
- Tan, H., Yan, L., Huang, L., Wang, Y., Li, H., & Chen, J. Y. (2017). Behavior of sisal fiber concrete cylinders externally wrapped with jute FRP. *Polymer Composites*, 38(9), 1910–1917. <https://doi.org/10.1002/PC.23761>
- UNITED NATIONS ENVIRONMENT PROGRAMME. INTERNATIONAL PROGRAMME ON CHEMICAL SAFETY. Flame Retardants: A General Introduction [S. 1.], 2020:
<http://www.inchem.org/documents/ehc/ehc/ehc192.htm>
- v Hospodarova, E. S. N. S. (2018). Characterization of cellulosic fibers by FTIR spectroscopy for their further implementation to building materials. *Am J Anal Chem*, 9, 303–310. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajac.2018.96023>
- Wiggins, K., Drummond, P., & Champod, T. H. (2004). A study in relation to the random distribution of four fibre types on clothing (incorporating a review of previous target fibre studies). *Science & Justice*, 44(3), 141–148. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1355-0306\(04\)71706-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1355-0306(04)71706-2)
- Roser M, Ritchie H, Ortiz-Ospina E (2019) World Population Growth. <https://ourworldindata.org/world-population-growth> Accessed 22 March 2022
- Yan, L., & Chouw, N. (2012a). Behavior and analytical modeling of natural flax fibre-reinforced polymer tube confined plain concrete and coir fibre-reinforced concrete: *Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1177/0021998312454691*, 47(17), 2133–2148. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998312454691>
- Yan, L., & Chouw, N. (2012b). Behavior and analytical modeling of natural flax fibre-reinforced polymer tube confined plain concrete and coir fibre-reinforced concrete: *Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1177/0021998312454691*, 47(17), 2133–2148. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998312454691>
- Yan, L., Kasal, B., & Huang, L. (2016). A review of recent research on the use of cellulosic fibres, their fibre fabric reinforced cementitious, geo-polymer and polymer composites in civil engineering. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 92, 94–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPOSITESB.2016.02.002>
- Zapata, F., Ortega-Ojeda, F. E., & García-Ruiz, C. (2022). Forensic examination of textile fibres using Raman imaging and multivariate analysis. *Spectrochimica Acta - Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SAA.2021.120695>
- Zhu, H. X., Yan, L. B., Zhang, R., & Qiu, X. M. (2012). Size-dependent and tunable elastic properties of hierarchical honeycombs with regular square and equilateral triangular cells. *Acta Materialia*, 60(12), 4927–4939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ACTAMAT.2012.05.009>